

Application of a Vertical Effective Crank–Slider Approach in Reconfigurable Buildings through Computer-Aided Algorithmic Modelling

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Elementary robotics mechanisms based on the effective crank–slider and four–bar kinematics methods have been applied in the past to develop architectural concepts of reconfigurable structures of planar rigid–bar linkages (Phocas et al., 2020; Phocas et al., 2019). The applications referred to planar structural systems interconnected in parallel to provide reconfigurable buildings with rectangular plan section. In enabling structural reconfigurability attributes within the spatial circular section buildings domain, a vertical setup of the basic crank–slider mechanism is proposed in the current paper. The kinematics mechanism is integrated on a column placed at the middle of an axisymmetric circular shaped spatial linkage structure. The definition of target case shapes of the structure is based on a series of numerical geometric analyses that consider certain architectural and construction criteria (i.e., number of structural members, length, system height, span, erectability etc.), as well as structural objectives (i.e., structural behavior improvement against predominant environmental actions) aiming to meet diverse operational requirements and lightweight construction. Computer-aided algorithmic modelling is used to analyze the system's kinematics, in order to provide a solid foundation and enable rapid adaptation for mechanisms that exhibit controlled reconfigurations. The analysis demonstrates the implementation of digital parametric design tools for the investigation of the kinematics of the system at a preliminary design stage, in avoiding thus time-demanding numerical analysis processes. The design process may further provide enhanced interdisciplinary performance-based design outcomes.

Keywords: *Reconfigurable Structures, Spatial Linkage Structures, Kinematics, Parametric Associative Design.*

INTRODUCTION

Structural shape adjustments serve features of adaptability with regard to external varying conditions, as required in the domains of responsive architecture and robotics. Enabled through technological advancements in materials,

as well as control systems and sensors, buildings may change their configuration in offering numerous advantages over fixed-shaped structures. These include erectability at various sites for temporary means, responsiveness to changing functional conditions and user needs, as

well as external loading and improvement of energy building performance (Christoforou et al., 2015). In this framework, reconfigurable structures developed in the last years include tensegrity structures (Motro et al., 2001), scissor-like systems (Akgün et al., 2010) and bar linkage systems (Phocas et al., 2020; Phocas et al., 2019). Reconfigurable structures are based on employment of embedded computation and mechanical actuators. Primary aim of related developments constitutes the minimization of the number of control components employed towards preserving low self-weight of the structure and achieving an energy efficient operation. In addition, the possibility of having multiple possible target configurations in the system kinematics gains significance.

The 'kinetic. Tower' comprises a transformable structural prototype based on its joints' kinematics (Kilian et al., 2006). The structure is an outrigger unitized system at the core interconnected through tension-only members. It provides bending deformations in response to external stimuli. The 'Muscle Tower' consists of six tensegrity units along the height with actuators employed instead of tension-only members (Hwang, 2006). Another transformable planar truss with lower horizontal elastomeric tubes has hydraulic actuators in place of diagonal compression members (Merali and Long, 2010). Further reconfigurable structural examples comprise the Variable Geometry Truss, a planar or spatial member structure with embedded hydraulic actuators (Miura and Furuya; 1985) and an aluminum tensegrity structure presented in (Sterk, 2003). Furthermore, an active tensegrity structure with struts of variable length is presented in (Adam and Smith; 2008).

A transformable scissor-like structure presented in (Akgün et al., 2010) consists of pairs of bars connected by a joint that allows motion to be transferred throughout the structure via mechanical actuators. The actuation mechanism is reduced to a one degree-of-freedom (DOF)

system by allowing only one component to rotate. Different shapes can be obtained by varying the joints' location or the bars' length. A design method for scissor-like systems for the provision of double scissor-pair units is documented in (Rosenberg, 2009). Transformable hyperbolic paraboloids and doubly-ruled surface structures is included in (Maden, Aktas and Korkmaz, 2015).

Linkage-based systems consist of interconnected rigid bars and lower-order pairs. The systems reconfigurability typically requires the use of a number of actuators according to the DOF. However, a multistep control sequence can be utilized to adjust the system joints from an initial to a target value using a single actuator. This method effectively reduces the system to a 1-DOF externally controlled kinematics system in each reconfiguration step. Rigid-bar linkage systems can be actuated based on a direct or cable-driven approach (Phocas et al., 2020; Phocas et al., 2019). Basic linkage systems have been investigated in simulations and experimentally to achieve multiple target configurations (Christoforou et al., 2019; Phocas, Christoforou and Matheou, 2015; Phocas et al., 2024). The structural concept involved parallel-connected planar linkages with a minimum number of actuators positioned at the supports and brakes (e.g., electromagnetic, hydraulic or pneumatic brakes) installed at the intermediate joints.

Following the multistep kinematics concept, a pin supported planar system may be connected to a linear or rotating actuator (i.e., 'effective 4-bar', E4B, mechanism), in order to stepwise adjust the system joints to the desired values. The 4-bar linkage is a planar mechanism composed of four rigid members: ground, input link, output link and coupler link. This mechanism is a closed loop kinematic chain with a 1-DOF. A stepwise reconfiguration sequence is implemented with two internal joints and the ground supports of the linkage unlocked in each step. In the cable-driven

approach, linear motion actuators are connected to the cables of the system. Similarly, a planar system with a pin and a sliding support may be connected to a linear motion actuator (i.e., ‘effective crank–slider’, ECS, mechanism). Each intermediate step involves the selective release of one joint in each closed-loop linkage. In the cable-driven approach, linear motion actuators are connected to the cables and a brake is also installed on the sliding support. The kinematics approaches enable preservation of low structural self-weight, simplicity and reduced energy consumption for the reconfigurations.

Both kinematics approaches have been further applied to a reconfigurable spatial torus-shaped structure of rigid-bar linkages (Matheou et al., 2023). Reconfigurations of the spatial system are provided by the active radial planar linkages.

In achieving reconfigurability in circular section structures of rigid-bar linkages, a vertical ECS mechanism is employed in the present paper. The mechanism has been proposed for reconfigurability of planar systems in (Christoforou et al., 2023; Phocas et al., 2021). In the current study, the structure consists of active radial planar linkages and passive peripheral connecting elements of adjustable length. The active radial planar linkages are pin supported on the ground and on a common vertical slider positioned at the middle of the spatial circular section structure. The vertical slider corresponds to a telescopic column that extends along the vertical axis of the axisymmetric spatial system. The current study demonstrates the kinematics concept through reconfiguration of a paraboloid shaped spatial structure to an ellipsoid one of same span and different height. The kinematics concept is described in the next section of the paper, followed by the definition of two spatial shapes of the structure (i.e., initial and target shape). The subsequent section of the paper refers to the parametric associative design methodology applied for simulation of the

reconfiguration process based on the vertical ECS mechanism. The last section of the paper includes the conclusions of the study.

VERTICAL EFFECTIVE CRANK–SLIDER APPROACH

The active planar bar linkages of the axisymmetric spatial circular section structure consist of serially connected members with rotational joints between them. The linkages are pin-connected on a vertical centrally placed slider and to the ground, as shown in figure 1. The slider moves only vertically through a corresponding linear actuator (e.g., hydraulic cylinder). Brakes (e.g., electromagnetic) are installed on all rotational joints of the mechanism. To define a generic 1-DOF mechanism, the reconfiguration approach employs stepwise selective releasing of one intermediate joint on either side of the vertical slider, while the pin joints at the supports always remain unlocked (i.e., three rotational joints on either side of the slider). In each step, one joint angle of the kinematics mechanism is adjusted on each linkage connected to the slider to its target value and remains locked for the subsequent steps. The procedure is repeated for the remaining joints until all joints of the mechanism are adjusted to their target values. In fact, the system becomes several crank-slider mechanisms that share the same slider. Thus, only one motion actuator fixed to the column in the middle of the structure suffices for the reconfiguration of the spatial system.

Figure 1
Vertical ECS approach for reconfigurations of the rigid-bar linkage system with a common slider

SHAPES MATHEMATICAL DEFINITION

A span ranging from 10 to 12 meters was determined as adequate to meet the architectural requirements. All configurations of the reconfigurable structure must adhere to a uniform span, as the supports of the structure remain pinned once deployed. The reconfiguration from an elliptic paraboloid to an ellipsoid assumes the center of the paraboloid is situated at ground level, establishing the ground surface as a plane of symmetry. Consequently, the elliptic configuration necessitates a vertical shift along the Z-axis, either upward or downward, to ensure that both shapes maintain a common span and share supports. An upward shift ($S > 0$) is preferred to augment user space. Accordingly, the mathematical expressions for the reference shapes of the current structure, i.e., the elliptic paraboloid and the ellipsoid, are presented as equations (1) and (2) respectively, with the center of the paraboloid considered as the origin of the coordinate system:

$$z = \frac{x^2}{a_{PAR}^2} + \frac{y^2}{b_{PAR}^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{x^2}{a_{ELL}^2} + \frac{y^2}{b_{ELL}^2} + \frac{(z - S)^2}{c_{ELL}^2} = 1 \quad (2)$$

The geometries under consideration are illustrated in figure 2.

The paraboloid shape was chosen for estimating the parameters of the approximated structure. The mathematical challenge involves approximating the curved 3D shapes with a structure composed of linear structural members. Given the axisymmetric characteristics of both shapes, the problem simplifies to a planar one. This entails defining an ellipse and a parabola as follows:

Figure 2
Reference axisymmetric configurations - idealized shapes for a span of 6.0 m ($a_{par} = a_{el} = 6$ m, $b_{par} = b_{el} = 2.25$ m): a) Isometric view; b) Elevation YZ

$$z_{para}(x) = \frac{x^2}{a_{para}^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{x^2}{a_{ell}^2} + \frac{z^2}{h_{ell}^2} = 1 \quad (4)$$

A numerical analysis algorithm was developed in MATLAB software (MATLAB and Statistics Toolbox, 2023) to estimate the paraboloid height for a given length, span and number of bars. Subsequently, the potential ellipsoid reconfiguration for a specified target height is also determined. The algorithm iteratively seeks an approximating structural system, whose height closely matches that of the parabola defined at each iteration, within a predefined tolerance.

More precisely, an initial value of h_{para} is provided to the algorithm. For simplicity, equation (4) solves the mathematical problem for a parabola showing upwards and starting at $[0, 0]$,

hence $z_{para}(6) = h_{para}$. After solution the shapes are translated/rotated to match the final structure geometry as required. a_{para}^2 is estimated based on equation (3), defining in this way the parabola equation. Subsequently, the approximating structural system is determined and consecutively

$$\frac{x^2}{a_{para}^2} - \left(z_{o,i} + \sqrt{(l_{bar}^2 - x_{o,i}^2)} \right) = 0, \text{ for } i = 1:n, \text{ where } [x_{o,1}, z_{o,1}] = [0,0]. \quad (5)$$

The roots of this equation, representing n solutions, correspond to the centres of the n circles but also to the nodes of the structural system where the linear bars intersect. The numerical solution iterates through different values of h_{para} till $|x_{o,n} - span| < x_{tol}$, indicating convergence when the last node of the structural system approaches the support point. Here, x_{tol} was set to 0.5 mm. The developed algorithm was applied to assess potential solutions that meet the required architectural specifications. The results are presented in Table 1, offering an overview of the investigated feasible solutions.

Span [m]	h_{para} [m]	No of bars [-]	l_{bar} [m]
10	2.971	16	0.75
12	4.808	16	1.0
12	7.458	16	1.25
12	9.847	16	1.5

Table 1
Possible paraboloid configurations for the investigated structure

$$\sqrt{\left| 1 - \frac{x^2}{a_{ell}^2} \right|} \cdot h_{ell} - \left(z_{o,i} + \sqrt{(l_{bar}^2 - (x - x_{o,i})^2)} \right) = 0, \text{ for } i = 1:n, \text{ where } [x_{o,1}, z_{o,1}] = [0, h_{ell}]. \quad (6)$$

The investigations of the second ellipsoid reconfiguration revealed that adopting a bar length of 1.0 m would result in insufficient height of the structure near the perimeter. Consequently, the decision was made to adopt 1 m long bars. To compensate for the lower height near the perimeter, the last two bars were rearranged to

assigning n circles with a radius of $r = l_{bar}$. The center coordinates $x_{o,i}$, $z_{o,i}$ of each circle are positioned at the intersection of the previous circle with the parabola. The first circle is drawn at [0 0]. The mathematical formulation of this numerical approach is the following:

Among the investigated scenarios, the second one appeared to be the most satisfying in meeting the architectural requirements. However, a numerical analysis was also conducted to estimate potential arrangements of the bars for approximating the ellipse shape, following a methodology similar to the one described above. Once again for simplicity reasons the ellipsoid was assumed to have its center at [0, 0] and the shape was subsequently translated as required. In this analysis, the height of the ellipse is set to $h_{ell} = 2.25$ m, adhering to the minimum allowed height based on architectural criteria. This time, the following equation is iteratively solved:

have a steeper slope, thereby increasing the overall height of the structure, figure 3.

b)

PARAMETRIC ASSOCIATIVE DESIGN

The kinematics approach refers to the system reconfiguration from an axisymmetric paraboloid to an axisymmetric ellipsoid shape of 12 m span. The spatial circular section structure consists of eight radial planar bar linkages connected on a central telescopic column (i.e., vertical slider). The length of the bars amounts to 1.0 m. The maximum height of the structure in its initial configuration amounts to 4.81 m, and in its target configuration, 3.15 m. The initial and target configurations of the spatial structure are presented in figure 4.

a)

b)

Figure 3
Adopted shape approximations with linear bar systems: a) Parabola; b) Ellipse

Figure 4
Spatial structure composed of active linkages and intermediate passive linkages; a) Paraboloid shape; b) Ellipsoid shape

Further shapes can be chosen based on specific criteria and objectives. The specific case study involves axisymmetric shapes of the structure (i.e., initial and target configuration), and the reconfiguration process is followed synchronously by all radial planar linkages of the system. Thus, the reconfiguration process is applied on a planar reference system of two bar linkages that share the same vertical slider.

A number of motion schedules are possible for a complete reconfiguration of the system from the initial to the target configuration. A most appropriate motion sequence may be selected upon considering different factors, including time-scale of transformations, functional, architectural criteria and objectives, and/or mechanical criteria (e.g., energy consumption, work done by the actuation system, brake torques, slider displacement, cable relative length variation etc.). The motion sequence applied

follows a clockwise order for the left bar linkage and an anticlockwise order for the right bar linkage, as shown in figure 5. Note that the direction of the slider's movement in each step depends on the corresponding joint angle

modification. An increase of the joint angle induces an upwards movement of the slider, while a decrease of the joint angle, a corresponding downwards movement.

Figure 5
Scheduling table
for reconfiguration
Sequence (⊗:
locked joint, ⊙:
unlocked joint, ⊖:
currently adjusted
joint, Δ: pivoted-
to-the-ground
joint, □: slider)

	ECS																	
	MOVEMENT	J ₁	J ₂	J ₃	J ₄	J ₅	J ₆	J ₇	J ₈	d ₉	J ₁₀	J ₁₁	J ₁₂	J ₁₃	J ₁₄	J ₁₅	J ₁₆	J ₁₇
Step 1	0.530	Δ	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	□	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	Δ
Step 2	-0.350	Δ	⊗	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	□	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊗	Δ
Step 3	-0.314	Δ	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	□	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊗	⊗	Δ
Step 4	0.100	Δ	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊗	□	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊗	Δ
Step 5	0.150	Δ	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊗	⊗	□	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	Δ
Step 6	0.310	Δ	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊗	□	⊗	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	Δ
Step 7	0.050	Δ	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊙	⊗	□	⊙	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	Δ
Step 8	-0.050	Δ	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊙	□	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	⊗	Δ

The parametric associative design methodology applied simulates the system's reconfiguration process based on the vertical effective crank-slider kinematics approach. Furthermore, dynamic computational tools allow the study of geometric properties and constraints for the exploration of kinetic form. Therefore, the methodology utilizes parametric tools such as Grasshopper plug-in for Rhinoceros software (Grasshopper, n.d.; Rhino 3D, n.d.) and Kangaroo plugin for Grasshopper (Kangaroo Physics, n.d.) as standard components.

The algorithmic modeling adopts four parts to achieve the described application of the spatial structure as shown in figure 6. The first part consists of assigning the coordinates of the points (x,y) through the points component in Grasshopper plug-in for Rhinoceros software. Thus, nine values were defined for each bar

linkage, which correlate to the number of joints of the system in the initial and target configuration. Correspondingly, a planar polyline of the structure was generated with flexible joints for each configuration. Furthermore, the polyline was exploded into eight segments, in order to calculate and predefine the desired angles between them. The initial joint angle values of the left bar linkage system in clockwise order are: $\theta_1 = [166.436]^T$; $\theta_2 = [169.115]^T$; $\theta_3 = [171.976]^T$; $\theta_4 = [174.093]^T$; $\theta_5 = [175.487]^T$; $\theta_6 = [176.488]^T$; $\theta_7 = [177.272]^T$, and the corresponding target joint angle values are: $\theta_1 = [177.203]^T$; $\theta_2 = [176.233]^T$; $\theta_3 = [175.740]^T$; $\theta_4 = [174.699]^T$; $\theta_5 = [171.081]^T$; $\theta_6 = [134.588]^T$; $\theta_7 = [155.147]^T$. Thus, two lists are generated to document the joint angle values. Note that joints₁₀₋₁₇ have mirrored coordinates to joints₁₋₈.

Figure 6
Bar-chart of
computer-aided
algorithmic
modelling for the
geometrical
characteristics'
definition of the
structure and the
kinematics
approach

The second part defines d_9 as the joint of the linear slider in the xy axis and J_1 and J_{17} as fixed joints of the planar system. Additionally, the vertical slider can accommodate range values of -1 to 2, in order to regulate the adjustment of height. Similarly, a spring domain and equal-length components were used to ensure that the segments in the structure maintained equal lengths of the bars, as well as the predetermined joint angles.

The next part of the algorithmic modelling is the adjustment of the initial joint angles to the target positions. In order to achieve the desired kinematics mechanism, the model includes constraints that are dependent on the reconfiguration sequence. The joints J_2 to J_{16} can be locked or unlocked to achieve a 1-DOF kinematics mechanism in each reconfiguration step, while d_9 is identified for the vertical slider and J_1 , J_{17} , for the fixed ground joints. The kinematics mechanism operates by adjusting d_9 with a slider in Grasshopper to attain the target angle of the adjusted joint. Next, the adjusted joint is set to a value of "1", in order to be locked to its position. In ensuring the appropriate direction of the two corresponding bars angle adjustment, a solver component in Kangaroo was utilized. The solver component applies all the parameters of the kinematics mechanism and plays a significant role for the operation of the mechanism. Relevant inputs include among others the length of the bars at 1 m and the

anchoring of ground joints J_1 and J_{17} with a corresponding high strength value. The solver component uses these inputs to provide the final output, which is then used to acquire the final target shape of the system.

In the last part of the algorithmic modelling, the planar polyline was positioned radially in corresponding circles with radius of 8 to create the 3D model of the structure. Finally, the main polyline was connected horizontally with a secondary polyline to create the wireframe of the structure. Through Grasshopper plug-in for Rhinoceros software, the structure's primary and secondary profiles were assigned to create the final spatial model in its initial and target shape.

The corresponding reconfiguration steps of the building structure are presented in figure 7. The various phases of the building structure reconfiguration are inherently connected to the reconfiguration process itself, that is defined by the motion sequence applied in the system's kinematics.

CONCLUSIONS

The kinematics approach of the vertical ECS has been proposed for the reconfiguration of an axisymmetric spatial bar linkage structure from an initial paraboloid shape to a target ellipsoid shape. The spatial structure consists of radial planar rigid-bar linkages that are externally pin supported on the ground and share a common slider on a column placed at the middle of the

Figure 7
Motion Sequence
based on the
vertical ECS
method for
stepwise
reconfigurations
of the system with
n serially
connected rigid
links (⊗: locked
joint, ○: unlocked
joint, Δ: pivoted-
to-the-ground
joint)

structure. The kinematics approach is based on the reduction of the system to an externally controlled 1-DOF mechanism in each successive step of the reconfiguration sequence. The approach enables provision of different intermediate and target shapes of the structure and minimum structural self-weight due to a single actuator employed, detached from the primary bar linkages of the structure.

The case study demonstrates the applicability of the reconfiguration approach to spatial circular section structures through parametric associative design. Future work includes the development of automated motion planning and optimization processes for the generation of optimal motion trajectories and sequences based on specific criteria and objectives.

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